

FUTURE DEMAND TO WATER

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Annotation. Calculations show that from 2010 to 2025 all water resources will be allocated for human activities, which means that water is likely to be sold as a source of investment. Globally, water consumption has increased six times in the last 100 years. If this situation continues, by 2025 humanity will need twice as much water as it does now.

Key words: future; water; health; life; drinking water; illness.

Water is a main source of surviving and human being development. Water is a key resources for living, food production, health, living a decent life and human development.

There is no life without water or such life is not known yet scientifically. As Organization of Health Protection informs 85 percent of all illnesses are connected with water. Every year 25 billion people die exactly because of such illnesses. Mankind uses average 75 tons of water during his life. During the year if water reserves is more than 1000 m³ and less than 1700 m³ per a man, the water deficient is in middle level. If it is less than 1000 m³, the water deficient gets its high level. So, how is condition in our life? In 1960 in our Republic this indication got 3760 m³. In 2000, it fell down till 1960. Presently it is a little higher than average water deficiency level. But drinking water reserves twice decreased for 40 year. In 2025 our population is expecting to be 35 billion. But it is fact that water will not increase.

Government of Uzbekistan made several decisions concerning development of safe water usage, reconstruction of water objects to provide guaranteed water. In the high part of Amudarya To'palang reservoir which contains 0,5 km³ is being built. And it is also being planned to build Shurbulok reservoir in the low part of Amudarya which is going to be 3,6 km³ the aim of which will be to provide guaranteed water delta ecosystem's demand in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The purpose of these actions is to increase the results of water supply and it gives an opportunity of redistribution and management of water.

92 percent of water is spent to agriculture. 4,3 billion hectares of country's territory is watered in our country. The water is used more than it must be used to water the sowing area.

As it is seen from above table, from 2010 to 2025 the demand of water will grow. That's why drinking water must be used in measure and for needs only.

Basin	The water demand to develop km ³										
	2010						2025				
	Mini mum		Opti mum		Maxi mum		Mini mum		Opti mum		Maxi mum
	mln.g a	km ³	mln.g a	Km ³	mln.g a	Km ³	mln.g a	Km ³	mln.g a	Km ³	mln. ga
Amu daryo	2,3	37	2,6	41	2,9	40	2,3	37	2,9	42	3,9
Sirdar yo	1,8	22	1,9	24	2,0	21	1,9	22	2,0	22	2,3
Total:	4,1	59	4,5	65	4,9	61	4,2	59	4,9	64	6,2

Drinking and communal water supply. In the future, the main tasks in this area will be to meet the needs of the city and settlements through centralized systems that provide the population with full quality drinking water, depending on the type and norms of water supply.

Short term is 6,2 km³ per a year (2010), mid-term future is 8,1 km³ per a year (2025). Water provision of agriculture. In this field provision of water will be redirected mainly to cattle-breeding, to satisfy the demands of agrochemical, technical and other service fields of farming and cattle-breeding. Its future demand will be followings:

Short-term future will be 1,5 km³ (2010) per a year

Mid-term future will be 1,7 km³ per a year (2025).

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